

1 Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Assessment of Licorice Supercritical

2 Extracts

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8 Abstract

9 Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) is a plant used widely in herbal medicines due to their
10 several biological potentials. The supercritical extraction of licorice roots was investigated to
11 assess the antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of the extracts. Extraction conditions were
12 pressures from 15 to 40 MPa, 313.15 and 333.15 K, and ethanol cosolvent in the range of 0 to
13 20% mass. In the case of high-pressure extractions using pure carbon dioxide (CO₂)
14 fractionation of the supercritical extract was accomplished in a two-cell decompression
15 system. Fractionation was carried out with the aim to examine the potential separation of the
16 antioxidant and antimicrobial licorice compounds and thus increase the bioactive properties
17 of the fractions obtained in each separation cell. Main licorice bioactive compounds,
18 liquiritin, liquiritigenin, glycyrrhizin, isoliquiritigenin and glabridin, were identified by
19 HPLC and quantified using standards. Extracts obtained with supercritical CO₂ and ethanol
20 cosolvent contain the higher amounts of phenolic compounds and also the higher antioxidant
21 activity but exhibit low or even no antimicrobial activity. Using pure CO₂ at high pressure
22 coupled with the on-line fractionation of the extract, two samples were obtained which
23 showed, respectively, lower phenolic compounds content and good antimicrobial capacity
24 (first fraction) and higher phenolic compounds content and antioxidant capacity (second

25 fraction). Thus, the advantages of supercritical on-line fractionation are demonstrated in the
26 extraction of Licorice roots.

27 **Keywords:** supercritical carbon dioxide, bioactive compounds, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, licorice,
28 antioxidant, antibacterial.

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Licorice is a ligneous perennial shrub typical of the Mediterranean region, Asia Minor and
31 Middle East and also widely cultivated in southern Russia and Iran (Ody, 2000). The roots
32 and rhizomes of licorice are used extensively in herbal medicines due to their, among others,
33 emollient, detoxification, anti-ulcer, anti-inflammatory, gastro-protective and anti-allergenic
34 properties (Mukhopadhyay and Panja, 2008). Licorice contains a variety of bioactive
35 compounds, different sugars, phenolic compounds, isoflavones, coumarins, stilbenoids and
36 saponins such as glycyrrhizin (Qiao et al., 2015), with positive pharmaceutical functions,
37 such as anti-inflammatory, anti-viral, anti-carcinogenic (Fukai et al., 2004; Hatano et al.,
38 2000), antifungal properties (Fatima et al., 2009), as well as antioxidant and antimicrobial
39 activities (Thakur et al., 2016). Different extraction procedures have been investigated to
40 obtain bioactive extracts from licorice roots, being water, ethanol and methanol, the main
41 solvents studied.

42 Visavadiya et al. (2009) and Gupta et al. (2016) reported the antioxidant activity of extracts
43 obtained by soxhlet extraction with ethanol and water. Hejazi et al. (2017) used the same
44 extraction technique, but with methanol solvent. Methanolic extracts were subsequently
45 fractionated with water and several organic solvents covering different polarities, in order to
46 evaluate the fractions for the *in vitro* antioxidant capacity and apoptotic effects in cell
47 systems. Cheel et al. (2010) and Tohma and Gulçin (2010) studied the radical scavenging
48 activity of extracts obtained by infusion using ethanol and water. Karami et al. (2015)
49 evaluated the antioxidant capacity of extracts obtained by microwave assisted extraction
50 (MAE) with water and 80% ethanol and methanol. From these works, polar solvents were
51 generally more effective to obtain extracts containing high concentrations of phenolic
52 compounds and better antioxidant capacities, specially water, ethanol and their mixtures.

53 Furthermore, the antioxidant activity of licorice extracts was strong related with the presence
54 of glycyrrhizin, a compound with an antioxidant mechanism studied and reported in the
55 literature (Beskina et al., 2006).

56 Recently, several studies aiming to expand the knowledge about the biological properties of
57 licorice extracts in regard to antimicrobial activity have been reported. Several studies have
58 shown the ability of licorice aqueous, ethanol and methanol extracts, obtained by different
59 extraction processes, to inhibit the growth of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, such
60 as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella spp.* (Chandra
61 and Gunasekaran, 2917, García-Ruiz et al., 2015, Astaf eva and Sukhenko, 2014, Escisli et
62 al., 2008). Based on the above inhibitory activities against bacteria, it has been suggested that
63 licorice may have a therapeutic and/or preventive capacity for oral infections (Gafner et al.,
64 2011).

65 Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) is an extraction technology also applied to obtain
66 antioxidant and antimicrobial extracts from natural sources (Fornari et al., 2012).
67 Supercritical fluids allow high extraction rates due to their high solvation power (liquid-like
68 density), low viscosities and high diffusion coefficients. Supercritical CO₂ (SCCO₂) is the
69 preferred supercritical fluid, due to its low critical temperature (304 K) and moderate critical
70 pressure (7.4 MPa), which prevents or minimizes the degradation of bioactive compounds.
71 Moreover, CO₂ is inexpensive, inert, non-toxic, non-flammable and allows obtaining solvent-
72 solvent free products. Despite these interesting properties, only a few studies have been
73 reported for the SFE of licorice roots and their objective was the extraction of glycyrrhizic
74 acid. Kim et al. (2004) examined the extraction behavior of this compound at different
75 pressures (11-50 MPa), temperatures (313-393 K) and using water and 70% aqueous
76 methanol as cosolvent. The best result (98% glycyrrhizic acid recovery) was obtained at 30

77 MPa, 343 K and 15% of aqueous methanol cosolvent. Likewise, Hedayati and Ghoreishi
78 (2015) studied glycyrrhizic acid extraction by a combined static-dynamic procedure at
79 several pressures (10-34 MPa), temperatures (318-358 K), dynamic extraction times (40-120
80 min), CO₂ flow rates (0.8-2 mL/min) and using different methanol/water mixtures as
81 cosolvent. The highest extraction (54% compound recovery) was reached at 30 MPa, 341 K,
82 extraction time of 108 min and 46.5% methanol (v/v). In a further contribution, Hedayati and
83 Ghoreishi (2016) studied the same extraction parameters but using water as cosolvent, and
84 determined the optimal conditions simulating the experimental results by an artificial neural
85 network model.

86 Based on this background, this work presents a study of the SFE of licorice roots using CO₂
87 with and without the addition of ethanol as a cosolvent and, for the first time, the *in vitro*
88 evaluation of the antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of the supercritical fractions obtained.

89 **2. Materials and methods**

90 **2.1. Chemicals**

91 Ethanol (99.5% purity) and Sodium Carbonate anhydrous (99.5% purity) were purchased
92 from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). CO₂ (N38) was supplied from Carbueros Metálicos (Madrid,
93 Spain). Gallic acid standard (> 98% purity), 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH, 95%
94 purity), 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS, ≥
95 95% purity), (±)-6-Hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchromane-2-carboxylic acid (Trolox, 97%
96 purity), Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent, chloramphenicol (≥ 98% purity), liquiritin, glabridin,
97 liquiritigenin, glycyrrhizic acid ammonium salt and isoliquiritigenin were purchased from
98 Sigma–Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Difco Wilkins-Chalgren Agar and BBL Mueller
99 Hinton II Broth was purchased from Becton, Dickinson and Company (France).

100 2.2. Sample preparation

101 Root of licorice harvested in Spain was obtained from Murciana herbalist's (Murcia, Spain)
102 and the water content was 9.90% wt. The sample was ground using a Premill 250 hammer
103 mill (Leal S.A., Granollers, Spain) and the mean particle size was 100 μm (all particles were
104 lower than 500 μm). All samples were stored in polyethylene bags under vacuum and kept at
105 4 °C until extraction.

106 2.3. Supercritical fluid extraction

107 A pilot-extractor (model SF2000; Thar Technology, Pittsburgh, PA, USA) was used for the
108 SFE assays. The extractor comprises a cylinder cell (0.273 L) and two separator-cells (S1 and
109 S2) (0.5 L capacity each), with independent control of temperature and pressure. A detailed
110 description of the equipment used can be found elsewhere (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017).
111 The experimental conditions are listed in Table 1. The mass of licorice root was 0.160 kg of
112 licorice root in all the experiments, being the apparent density of the packed bed 586 kg/m^3
113 (estimated porosity of 0.7). Different extractions were accomplished at 15-40 MPa, 313.15
114 and 333.15 K, and two CO₂ flow rates, 50 and 70 g/min, during 3 h in dynamic extraction (no
115 static extraction was applied), representing a CO₂/plant ratio of 56 and 79 kg/kg, respectively.
116 Ethanol was used as a cosolvent, being the concentration of ethanol in the supercritical
117 extractive solvent in the range 0 to 20% wt (CO₂/ethanol ratio of 4 kg/kg). CO₂ and the
118 cosolvent were mixed in the desire ratio previous to be pumped into the extraction cell.

119 The extracts were obtained by reducing pressure in the separator-cells. In the case of runs 1 to
120 6 (Table1) both separators were maintained at the system recirculation pressure (5 MPa) and
121 the extracted material was recovered from S1 and S2 and mixed in a single fraction.
122 Moreover, runs 7 to 10 were carried out at higher pressures and the extract was fractionated
123 in the decompression cascade system comprising two separators. For this purpose, the first

124 separator vessel (S1) was kept at 15 MPa and the second one was maintained at the
125 recirculation pressure (5 MPa). Thus, two fractions (S1 and S2) were collected in each of the
126 runs 7 to 10.

127 **2.4. HPLC analysis**

128 HPLC analysis was performed as previously described by the authors Wei et al. (2015). A
129 Prominence-i LC-2030C 3D Plus (Shimadzu) equipped with a quaternary solvent delivery
130 system, an autosampler and DAD detector and RP-C18 (250 × 4.6 mm; 3 µm) was used. The
131 column temperature was set at 25 °C. The mobile phase consists of acetonitrile (A) and
132 0.026% aqueous H₃PO₄ (v/v), applying the following gradient elution: at 0-20 min, 20%-
133 25% A, 20-30 min, 25% -34% A, 30-50 min, 34%-50% A, 50-60 min, 50% -60% A and 60-
134 80 min, 60% A. After 5 min, the initial conditions were achieved. The flow rate was 0.7
135 ml/min and was kept constant during analysis. Injection volume was 20 µl and detection was
136 accomplished at 254, 280 and 370 nm. Calibration curves with the standards were used to
137 determine the content of these bioactive compounds in the different extracts.

138 **2.5. Total phenolic compounds (TPC) determination**

139 The total phenolic content in licorice extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu
140 method (Singleton et al., 1999). Briefly, 50 µl of extract were mixed with 3 mL of milliQ
141 water and 250 µl of Folin Ciocalteu reagent. The content was thoroughly mixed and after 3
142 min, 750 µl of sodium carbonate solution (20% mass) and 950 µl of milliQ water were added
143 to the mixture. After 2 h at room temperature and remained in darkness, the absorbance was
144 measured at 760 nm using a Genesys 10S UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fischer
145 Scientific Inc., MA, USA). The results were expressed as GAE (mg of gallic acid
146 equivalents/g of extract). All analyses were done in triplicate.

147 **2.6. Antioxidant capacity**

148 **2.6.1. ABTS assay**

149 The antioxidant capacity of the extracts was determined by the ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging
150 assay following the method described by Re et al. (1999). ABTS^{•+} radical cation was
151 generated by mixing ABTS^{•+} stock solution (7 mM) with 2.45 mM potassium persulfate after
152 incubation of the mixture at room temperature for 16 h under darkness. Once the ABTS^{•+}
153 radical was formed, the solution absorbance was adjusted to 0.700 ± 0.02 at 734 nm by
154 ethanol in a Genesys 10S UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fischer Scientific Inc., MA,
155 USA). Afterwards, 990 μ L of ABTS^{•+} solution was added to 10 μ L of sample and the reaction
156 mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature and under darkness, until the absorbance
157 reached a plateau. The absorbance was recorded at 734 nm and the results were expressed as
158 IC₅₀ value (**Inhibitory concentration**: concentration of extract necessary to inhibit the initial
159 concentration of radical by **50%**), as well as Trolox equivalents (TEAC) (μ mol Trolox/g
160 extract), which were calculated taking into account the Trolox standard and sample
161 concentrations that produce the scavenging of **50%** of ABTS^{•+} radical. All the analyses were
162 carried out in triplicate.

163 **2.6.2. DPPH assay**

164 The ability of extracts to scavenge DPPH free radicals was determined according to the
165 method described by Brand-Williams et al. (1995). Licorice extract were added to 975 μ L of
166 DPPH radical in ethanol ($6.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$), which was daily prepared. The reaction took place at
167 room temperature in the dark until it reached a plateau. Then, the absorbance was measured
168 at 515 nm in a Genesys 10S UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fischer scientific, MA,
169 USA). A calibration curve (linear regression) was used to determine the DPPH concentration

170 in the reaction medium. A control sample (i.e. a sample comprising the same volume of
171 solvent instead of extract) was used to measure the maximum DPPH absorbance. Trolox was
172 used as reference standard, so results were expressed as TEAC values ($\mu\text{mol Trolox/g}$
173 extract), as well as IC_{50} value ($\mu\text{g/mL}$). All analyses were done in triplicate.

174 **2.7. Antibacterial activity assay**

175 The extracts and fractions collected were individually tested against a Gram-positive bacteria,
176 *Staphylococcus aureus* American Type Culture Collection-ATCC 25923 and a Gram-
177 negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922. A broth microdilution method was used, as
178 recommended by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS, 1999),
179 for determination of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). All tests were performed
180 in Mueller–Hinton broth supplemented with 0.5% tween 20. The inocula of bacterial strains
181 were prepared from overnight Mueller–Hinton broth cultures at 37 °C. Test strains were
182 suspended in Muller–Hinton (bacteria) broth to give a final density 10^7 cfu/mL. The extract
183 and fractions were diluted in ethanol ranging from 50 to 1 mg/mL.

184 The 96-microwell plates were prepared by dispensing into each well 185 μl of culture broth,
185 10 μl of the different extracts dilutions, antibiotic solution (chloramphenicol as positive
186 control) or solvent (ethanol as negative control), and 5 μl of the inoculums. In addition,
187 blanks were prepared adding 190 μL of broth medium to the solvent or extracts wells. The
188 final volume of each well was 200 μl . After dispensing the inoculum, the plates were read in
189 an Infinite 200 PRO plate reader (TECAN, Trading AG, Switzerland) spectrophotometer at
190 620 nm for T0 (Zero Time). Then, the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and the
191 absorbance was read for TF (Final Time). Each test was performed in triplicate and repeated
192 twice.

193 The inhibition percentage was calculated following the method described by Cueva et al.
194 (2010) as (Eq. 1):

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \left(1 - \frac{(\text{TF}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{T0}_{\text{Sample}}) - (\text{TF}_{\text{Blank of sample}} - \text{T0}_{\text{Blank of sample}})}{(\text{TF}_{\text{Growth}} - \text{T0}_{\text{Growth}}) - (\text{TF}_{\text{Blank}} - \text{T0}_{\text{Blank}}} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

195 Where $\text{TF}_{\text{Sample}}$ and $\text{T0}_{\text{Sample}}$ corresponded to the absorbance at 620 nm of the strain growth
196 in the presence of the licorice extracts after and before incubation, respectively;
197 $\text{TF}_{\text{Blank of sample}}$ and $\text{T0}_{\text{Blank of sample}}$ corresponded to the broth medium with extracts after
198 and before incubation, respectively; $\text{TF}_{\text{Growth}}$ and $\text{T0}_{\text{Growth}}$ correspond to the strain growth
199 in the presence of the solvents after and before incubation; and TF_{Blank} and T0_{Blank}
200 corresponded to the broth medium with solvent after and before incubation.

201 For active extracts, the survival parameter IC_{50} value was defined as the concentration
202 required to obtain 50% inhibition of growth after 24 hours of incubation at 37 °C and was
203 estimated by nonlinear regression using the sigmoidal dose-response (with variable slope)
204 equation (2):

$$Y = \text{Bottom} + \frac{(\text{Top} - \text{Bottom})}{(1 + 10^{(\log \text{IC}_{50} - X) \times \text{Slope}})} \quad (2)$$

205 where, X represents the logarithm of concentration, Y is the % Inhibition which starts at the
206 Bottom and goes to the Top with a sigmoid shape, Log IC_{50} is the logarithmic of IC_{50} , and
207 Slope represents the slope parameter. The PRISM program (GraphPad Software, Inc.) was
208 used for the approximation of the four parameters. For each data set, comparison of the fit to
209 the previous sigmoidal dose response model (4 parameters) was carried out using PRISM,

210 and also the fit to the same model with the Bottom and Top parameters constrained,
211 respectively, to 0 and 100% was possible.

212 3. Results and Discussion

213 3.1. Supercritical Fluid Extraction

214 The experimental conditions applied for the SFE of licorice roots, as well as extraction yield
215 obtained (mass of extract/mass of licorice) are reported in Table 1. As can be observed, the
216 extraction yields ranged from 0.66% (run 1) to 3.07 % (run 6).

217 With regard to the effect of pressure (Table 1, runs 1 and 7), a rise in this parameter
218 considerably increased the extraction yield. In this sense, when no cosolvent is used, an
219 extraction yields 2.7-fold higher was reached at 30 MPa (1.76%) in comparison with yield at
220 15 MPa (0.66%). Temperature effect seem to exhibit crossover behavior, since at 40 MPa a
221 temperature rise produced a yield increase (runs 8 and 10), but at 30 MPa the same
222 temperature rise resulted in a yield decrease (runs 7 and 9).

223 Indeed, the use of ethanol had a considerably influence over the amount of extract obtained.
224 In this respect, the addition of 10% cosolvent at 15 MPa and 70 g/min (run 2) implied an
225 extraction yield 3.3-fold higher than the obtained without ethanol (run 1). This effect is
226 clearly represented in the Figure 1. As it is showed, the extraction yields linearly increased
227 ($r^2= 0.960$) with the addition of cosolvent in the range studied. Maximum yield is obtained in
228 run 6 (3.07%) when the maximum amount of ethanol (20%) is used. These results are in
229 agreement with the analysis reported by Hedayati and Ghoreishi (2015) concerning the yield
230 and recovery of glycyrrhizin (no total yields were reported) in the supercritical extractions
231 carried out using methanol: water mixtures as modifier, in percentages up 5% (v/v).

232 Furthermore, Kim et al. (2004) also highlighted the relevant effect of methanol: water as CO₂
233 modifier to extract the same compound, glycyrrhizin, from licorice root.

234 The influence of the amount of cosolvent over yield is especially relevant if it is compared to
235 the yields obtained at higher pressure. Despite the increase in the solvation power as a
236 consequence of the higher density of CO₂ when pressure rises from 15 to 30 MPa at a
237 constant temperature, the extraction yield obtained at 15 MPa, 70 g/min and 10% cosolvent
238 (2.19%) was -1.25-fold higher than the obtained at 30 MPa at the same flow rate but without
239 cosolvent (1.76%).

240 The yields obtained in the fractions S1 and S2 collected in runs 7 to 10 are given in Table 2.
241 In general, most of extract was recovered in the second separator, with yields up to 8 times
242 higher than the yield obtained in the first separator.

243 **3.2. Total phenolic compounds (TPC) and antioxidant capacity**

244 Table 3 shows the amount of TPC (mg GAE/g extract) in the extracts obtained at the different
245 experimental conditions and their antioxidant capacity expressed as IC₅₀ (µg extract/mL) and
246 TEAC value (µmol trolox/g extract) as determined by the ABTS and DPPH assays.

247 The TPC content varied from 48.47 (run 8-S1) to 180.06 mg GAE/g extract (run 6). The
248 lower concentrations were obtained by using pure CO₂ (run 1) and particularly in the first
249 fraction (S1) of runs 7 to 10. The higher concentrations of TPC were obtained when ethanol
250 was used and, at constant pressure of 30 MPa, 313 K of temperature and 50 g/min of CO₂
251 flow rate, TPC increased linearly ($r^2 = 0.979$) as the amount of ethanol did (Figure 2). The
252 concentrations of TPC obtained in the SFE licorice extracts were higher than those reported
253 in other studies. The TPC extracted in run 6 (180.06 mg GAE/g extract) was almost 4-fold
254 higher than the obtained with 80% ethanol by MAE (Karami et al., 2015, 2013), and 7.7, 3.8

255 and 2.3-fold higher than the achieved using, respectively, water (Gupta et al., 2016), ethanol
256 (Visavadiya et al., 2009) and methanol (Hejazi et al., 2017) by Soxhlet extraction.

257 The effect of supercritical solvent flow on TPC can be analysed by comparison of the values
258 obtained for runs 2 and 4, which were carried out at 15 MPa, 313 K, 10% ethanol cosolvent
259 and, respectively, 70 and 50 g/min CO₂ (total supercritical solvent flow of 77.8 and 55.6
260 g/min). The increase of flow resulted in a decrease of TPC from 163.03 to 141.18 mg GAE /g
261 extract probably due to the co-extraction of substances other than phenolics, as can be
262 inferred from the higher yield obtained in run 2 (almost 10% higher).

263 Regarding the effect of pressure and temperature on TPC, Figure 3 show the total amount of
264 TPC extracted (S1+S2 samples) in runs 7 to 10 as a function of pressure, together with the
265 total yield obtained in these runs. As can be observed in the figure, the TPC values show the
266 same crossover behaviour described previously concerning extraction yield. Then, it can be
267 concluded that at 30 MPa the increase of temperature decrease total yield and TPC content,
268 while at 40 MPa an increase of temperature increase total yield and TPC content.

269 Regarding the antioxidant capacity, the ABTS and DPPH assays show the same tendency, as
270 it can be deduced from the relation between the IC₅₀ values depicted in Figure 4. As in the
271 case of TPC, the antioxidant capacity increased with the amount of ethanol, so the highest
272 values were reached with 20% cosolvent (556 and 760 µmol/g for the ABTS and DPPH
273 assay). Nevertheless, despite the linear tendency TPC-%ethanol (Figure 2), no linear
274 correlation between the amount of ethanol and the antioxidant capacity was observed, with a
275 significant increase in the antioxidant capacity of the extract obtained with 20% ethanol (run
276 6) assessed by both the ABTS and DPPH assay. Moreover, the TEAC values exhibit a
277 general trend to increase with increasing TPC (Figure 5), but TEAC and TPC values could
278 not be linearly correlated for both the ABTS and DPPH assay. Several studies related a strong

279 and positive correlation between TPC and antioxidant activity (Casagrande et al., 2018;
280 Skotti et al., 2014). Nevertheless, this trend is not always satisfied and maybe related to the
281 presence of antioxidants other than phenolic compounds, such as carotenoids, ascorbic acid,
282 among others (Millao and Uquiche, 2016; Rufino et al., 2010). In the case of supercritical
283 licorice root extracts, other no-phenolic compounds may be present (although were not
284 analyzed in this work), in particularly those comprising licorice essential oil, which may also
285 contribute to the antioxidant activity (e.g. estragole, eugenol and anethol (Fenwick et al.,
286 1990) and thus, no linear relation between TPC and TEAC values was obtained.

287 Taking into account that lower IC_{50} values indicates a stronger radical scavenging activity,
288 the extract obtained in run 6, at 15 MPa, 50 g/min CO_2 and 20% cosolvent (IC_{50} 7.74 and
289 18.59 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, in ABTS and DPPH assays) showed a considerably higher
290 antioxidant capacity than extracts which were obtained from licorice using water or organic
291 solvents and other extraction techniques. In this regard, the IC_{50} of run 6 extract was around
292 75-fold lower than the obtained by Gupta et al. (2008) with ethanolic extracts (575 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
293 and 1424 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in ABTS and DPPH assay, respectively), as well as 7.4 (ABTS assay) and
294 1.5 (DPPH assay) fold lower than the obtained by Visavadiya et al. (2009) with the same
295 solvent. Hejazi et al. (2017) obtained DPPH IC_{50} values of 71.93 and 77.86 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in
296 methanol and chloroform fractions, respectively, so the IC_{50} of run 6 extract was 3.9 and 4.2
297 times lower than the obtained with these two organic solvents. In the case of the water extract
298 obtained by Thakur et al. (2016) by means of sonication (IC_{50} value of 189.9 and 334.7
299 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for DPPH and ABTS assay), our run 6 supercritical extract showed an efficacy to
300 scavenge these free radicals between 10.2 (DPPH assay) and 18.0 (ABTS assay) fold higher.
301 Furthermore, extracts with similar antioxidant capacity were obtained using pure CO_2 at high
302 pressure (30 and 40 MPa) and 333.15 K by fractionation of the extract at 15 MPa (S2
303 fractions of runs 9 and 10).

304 3.3. Antibacterial activity

305 Antimicrobial activity of licorice extracts against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, as representative of
306 Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, was evaluated as the inhibition of the bacterial
307 growth, and expressed as the IC₅₀ parameter. The antimicrobial assays showed that licorice
308 extracts can inhibit the growth of the evaluated bacteria. The IC₅₀ values (mg/ml)
309 corresponding to the inhibition of *E. coli* (ATCC 25299) and *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) are
310 given in Table 4.

311 In general, results of antimicrobial activity showed that *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 (Gram-
312 positive) was more resistant (higher IC₅₀ values) than *E. coli* ATCC 25299 (Gram-negative)
313 to the antimicrobial effect of all extracts tested. These results are in agreement with the data
314 presented by Chandra and Gunasekaran (2017) in their study of licorice extracts obtained by
315 solid-liquid extraction with chloroform solvent. A greater susceptibility of *E. coli* than *S.*
316 *aureus* to other antimicrobial materials was also reported by other authors (García-Ruiz et al.,
317 2015). The structures of cell envelope (cytoplasmic membrane and cell wall component),
318 which differ between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, may influence these
319 observed results. Antimicrobial agents commonly contact the cell envelope first and thus, the
320 structural differences produce a key role in the antimicrobial susceptibility. In particular, the
321 extracts obtained using ethanol (higher contents of phenolic compounds, runs 2 to 6), exhibit
322 lower and even no antimicrobial activity in comparison with the extract produced with pure
323 CO₂ (run 1). On the other hand, fractions obtained in the first separator (lower content of
324 phenolic compounds) exhibited the best antimicrobial activity for both bacteria. These
325 findings indicate that licorice antimicrobial compounds are soluble in CO₂ at pressures higher
326 than 15 MPa and can be concentrated by cascade decompression of high pressure SFE. It

327 suggests that antimicrobial activity of licorice extracts seems to be dependent on the type of
328 phenolic structure rather than the total content of phenolic compounds.

329 **3.4. HPLC analysis**

330 The major bioactive constituents of licorice are glycyrrhizin and several flavonoids, such as
331 liquiritin, isoliquiritin and their aglycones. These compounds are supposed as the active
332 principles responsible for its pharmacological efficacy (Zhang and Ye, 2009). The bioactive
333 compounds identified in this work by HPLC analysis were five compounds: liquiritin (RT:
334 12.80 min), liquiritigenin (RT: 35.06 min), glycyrrhizic acid ammonium salt (glycyrrhizin)
335 (RT: 48.21), isoliquiritigenin (RT: 49.73 min) and glabridin (RT: 69.15 min). The results of
336 the HPLC analysis are presented in Table 5. In the case of experiments accomplished with
337 on-line fractionation (runs 7 to 10), the compound concentrations obtained in the total extract
338 (S1+S2 fractions) are also reported in Table 5.

339 The most abundant compound found in all the extracts obtained in this work is glabridin, a
340 compounds well-characterized in the literature due to several important biological activities
341 such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-atherogenic (Asl and Hosseinzadeh, 2008;
342 Simmler et al., 2013). Extract obtained using pure CO₂ in run 1 contains 49.50 ± 0.14 mg
343 glabridin per g extract. Without cosolvent, the concentration of glabridin in the extract (mg
344 glabridin / g extract) increases with pressure, as is represented in Figure 6 for runs 1, 7 and 8
345 (313.15 K, 70 g/min of CO₂ without cosolvent). Nevertheless, glabridin recovery (mg
346 glabridin / g root) seem to attain a maximum around 30 MPa. Significantly higher glabridin
347 concentration and recovery were obtained when ethanol is used as cosolvent. Moreover, an
348 increase of ethanol cosolvent produces a decrease in glabridin concentration (runs 3 to 6 in
349 Tables 5) probably due to the simultaneous extraction of other compounds (and according
350 with the increase of extraction yield observed). In relation with the samples obtained by

351 supercritical fractionation, temperature seems to affect significantly glabridin fractionation
352 since fractions obtained in S1 at 313.15 K present lowest concentration of glabridin than the
353 corresponding S2 fraction (runs 7 and 8) while the opposite behavior was found at 333.15 K
354 (runs 9 and 10).

355 Another metabolite identified in all samples was liquiritin, which is a flavone observed in the
356 sweetening agent licorice and has been associate with anti-inflammatory effects (Gao et al.,
357 2017). Liquiritin content slightly increase with the percentage of ethanol and considerably
358 lower amounts of this compound were quantified in all samples (0.2-1.2 mg/g) in comparison
359 with glabridin (26-198 mg/g).

360 Among phenolic compounds in licorice are typically isoliquiritigenin and liquiritigenin
361 (Kondo et al., 2007). These were identified and quantified in the extracts of runs 2, 3, 4, 5 and
362 6, observing an increase of their concentration with the increase of the percentage of ethanol
363 cosolvent. Thus, these compounds could not be quantified in the supercritical fractionation
364 assays (runs 7 to 10) since no ethanol was used as cosolvent and despite the higher extraction
365 pressures applied. On the contrary, the content of triterpenoid glycyrrhizin was found to
366 decrease with increasing ethanol cosolvent and thus, it was not possible to quantify this
367 compound in runs 4, 5 and 6 while it was identified and quantified in all samples obtained in
368 runs 7 to 10. Glycyrrhizin is an important ingredient in various medicines, such as
369 antimicrobial, anti-ulcer, anti-hepatotoxic and antiviral formulas (Cinatl et al., 2003;
370 Dehpour et al., 1995). Yet, plant extracts use to be much more effective than isolated
371 compounds, as highlighted Cheel et al. (2010) for the case of licorice aqueous extracts.

372 Figure 6 shows the effect of pressure on glycyrrhizin concentration in the extract and
373 recovery per gram of root extracted. The figure refers to runs 1, 7 and 8 (313.15 K, 70 g/min
374 of CO₂ without cosolvent). Glycyrrhizin concentration show a slight decrease with increasing

375 pressure, but the recovery attains a maximum close to 30 MPa, similarly to glabridin. Yet,
376 this maximum recovery is lower than 1.5 mg /g root, considering the content of glycyrrhizin
377 in licorice root reported by Kim et al. (2004) (138 mg glycyrrhizin / g root). Nevertheless,
378 Kim et al. (2004) could not extract glycyrrhizin with pure supercritical CO₂ even applying
379 pressures of 50 MPa. Hedayati and Ghoreishi (2015) reported a maximum glycyrrhizin
380 recovery of 54% (74 mg glycyrrhizin / g root) when using methanol: water as CO₂ cosolvent,
381 which is a value significantly higher than the maximum recovery obtained in this work using
382 ethanol cosolvent (4.6 mg glycyrrhizin/g root).

383 Concerning the relation between the compounds detected and the biological activities
384 observed (antioxidant and antibacterial) in supercritical extracts, it can be stated that the
385 content of liquiritigenin and isoliquiritigenin do not affect the antibacterial activity, since
386 these compounds were not detected in the most active extracts (S1 fractions and extract of
387 run 1). Furthermore, the content of glabridin seems not to affect the antibacterial activity of
388 these most active extracts (Figure 7). On the contrary, regarding the antioxidant activity a
389 dependence of the antioxidant capacity on glabridin content is observed, as depicted in Figure
390 8 for all licorice supercritical extracts obtained in this work.

391 **4. Conclusions**

392 Supercritical licorice roots extracts were obtained using different extraction conditions to
393 investigate the viability of producing antioxidant and/or antimicrobial fractions. Two
394 strategic approaches were investigated: the effect of using ethanol as a polar cosolvent and
395 the effect of supercritical fractionation using a two-cell cascade decompression system.

396 In general, licorice supercritical extracts obtained in this work present considerably higher
397 antioxidant activity in comparison with extracts produced using liquid solvents (methanol,
398 chloroform, ethanol, water) as reported in the literature. As expected, the higher contents of

399 phenolic compounds were obtained in the extracts produced with supercritical CO₂ and
400 ethanol cosolvent, which in turn exhibit the higher antioxidant activity. The extraction yield
401 and total phenolic compounds content varies linearly with the amount of ethanol used.
402 Nevertheless, this linear correlation was not observed in regards the antioxidant activity.
403 Furthermore, the increase of the content of glabridin favors the antioxidant activity of the
404 extract.

405 On the other hand, the extracts produced with supercritical CO₂ and ethanol cosolvent show
406 low or even no antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* ATCC 25299 and *S. aureus* ATCC
407 25923. In this respect, high pressure extraction (30-40 MPa) using pure CO₂ and on-line
408 fractionation resulted in a first fraction (at 15 MPa) with a better antimicrobial effect although
409 with lower content of phenolic compounds.

410 The study concludes and highlights the capability of supercritical fractionation applied to
411 licorice roots to selective separate substances and to obtain antimicrobial and antioxidant
412 fractions.

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418 **References**

- 419 Asl, M.N., Hosseinzadeh, H., 2008. Review of pharmacological effects of *Glycyrrhiza* sp.
420 and its bioactive compounds. *Phyther. Res.* 22, 709–724.
421 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.2362>
- 422 Astaf'eva, O. V., Sukhenko, L.T., 2014. Comparative analysis of antibacterial properties and
423 chemical composition of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. from Astrakhan region (Russia) and
424 Calabria region (Italy). *Bull. Exp. Biol. Med.* 156, 829–832.
425 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10517-014-2462-8>
- 426 Badr, A.E., Omar, N., Badria, F.A., 2011. A laboratory evaluation of the antibacterial and
427 cytotoxic effect of liquorice when used as root canal medicament. *Int. Endod. J.* 44, 51–
428 58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2591.2010.01794.x>
- 429 Beskina, O.A., Abramov, A.I., Gabdulkhakova, A.G., Miller, A. V, Safronova, V.G.,
430 Zamaraeva, M. V, 2006. Possible mechanisms of antioxidant activity of glycyrrhizic
431 acid. *Biomed. Khim.* 52, 60–68.
- 432 Brand-Williams, W., Cuvelier, M.E., Berset, C., 1995. Use of a Free Radical Method to
433 Evaluate Antioxidant Activity 28, 25–30.
- 434 Casagrande, M., Zanela, J., Wagner, A., Busso, C., Wouk, J., Iurckevicz, G., Montanher,
435 P.F., Yamashita, F., Malfatti, C.R.M., 2018. Influence of time, temperature and solvent
436 on the extraction of bioactive compounds of *Baccharis dracunculifolia*: In vitro
437 antioxidant activity, antimicrobial potential, and phenolic compound quantification. *Ind.*
438 *Crops Prod.* 125, 207–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INDCROP.2018.08.088>
- 439 Chandra, J.H., Gunasekaran, H., 2017. Scening of phytochemical, antimicrobial and
440 antioxidant activity of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root extract. *J. Environ. Biol.* 38, 161–165.
- 441 Cheel, J., Antwerpen, P. Van, Tũ Mová, L., Onofre, G., Vokurková, D., Zouaoui-Boudjeltia,
442 K., Vanhaeverbeek, M., Nève, J., 2010. Free radical-scavenging, antioxidant and

443 immunostimulating effects of a licorice infusion (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.). Food Chem.
444 122, 508–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.02.060>

445 Cinatl, J., Morgenstern, B., Bauer, G., Chandra, P., Rabenau, H., Doerr, H.W., 2003.
446 Glycyrrhizin, an active component of liquorice roots, and replication of SARS-
447 associated coronavirus. Lancet (London, England) 361, 2045–6.

448 Cueva, C., Moreno-Arribas, M.V., Martín-Álvarez, P.J., Bills, G., Vicente, M.F., Basilio, A.,
449 Rivas, C.L., Requena, T., Rodríguez, J.M., Bartolomé, B., 2010. Antimicrobial activity
450 of phenolic acids against commensal, probiotic and pathogenic bacteria. Res. Microbiol.
451 161, 372–382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2010.04.006>

452 Dehpour, A.R., Zolfaghari, M.E., Samadian, T., Kobarfard, F., Faizi, M., Assari, M., 1995.
453 Antiulcer activities of liquorice and its derivatives in experimental gastric lesion induced
454 by ibuprofen in rats. Int. J. Pharm. 119, 133–138. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5173(94)00377-H)
455 [5173\(94\)00377-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-5173(94)00377-H)

456 Ercisli, S., Coruh, I., Gormez, A., 2008. Total phenolics, mineral contents, antioxidant and
457 antibacterial activities of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. roots grown wild in Turkey. Ital. J. food
458 20, 91–100.

459 Fatima, A., Gupta, V.K., Luqman, S., Negi, A.S., Kumar, J.K., Shanker, K., Saikia, D.,
460 Srivastava, S., Darokar, M.P., Khanuja, S.P.S., 2009. Antifungal activity of *Glycyrrhiza*
461 *glabra* extracts and its active constituent glabridin. Phyther. Res. 23, 1190–1193.
462 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.2726>

463 Fenwick, G.R., Lutomski, J., Nieman, C., 1990. Liquorice, *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.—
464 Composition, uses and analysis. Food Chem. 38, 119–143. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-8146(90)90159-2)
465 [8146\(90\)90159-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-8146(90)90159-2)

466 Fornari, T., Vicente, G., Vázquez, E., García-Risco, M.R., Reglero, G., 2012. Isolation of
467 essential oil from different plants and herbs by supercritical fluid extraction. J.

468 Chromatogr. A 1250, 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.04.051>

469 Fukai, T., Oku, Y., Hano, Y., Terada, S., 2004. Antimicrobial activities of hydrophobic 2-
470 arylbenzofurans and an isoflavone against vancomycin-resistant enterococci and
471 methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Planta Med.* 70, 685–687.
472 <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2004-827196>

473 Gafner, S., Bergeron, C., Villinski, J.R., Godejohann, M., Kessler, P., Cardellina, J.H.,
474 Ferreira, D., Feghali, K., Grenier, D., 2011. Isoflavonoids and coumarins from
475 *Glycyrrhiza uralensis*: antibacterial activity against oral pathogens and conversion of
476 isoflavans into isoflavan-quinones during purification. *J. Nat. Prod.* 74, 2514–2519.
477 <https://doi.org/10.1021/np2004775>

478 Gaitry Chopra, P.K.P., Saraf, B.D., Inam, F., Deo, S.S., 2013. Antimicrobial and antioxidant
479 activities of methanol extract roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* and hplc analysis. *Int. J.*
480 *Pharmy Pharm. Sci.* 5, 157–160.

481 Gao, Y.-X., Cheng, B.-F., Lian, J.-J., Guo, D.-D., Qin, J.-W., Zhang, Y.-B., Yang, H.-J.,
482 Wang, M., Wang, L., Feng, Z.-W., 2017. Liquiritin, a flavone compound from licorice,
483 inhibits IL-1 β -induced inflammatory responses in SW982 human synovial cells. *J.*
484 *Funct. Foods* 33, 142–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2017.03.039>

485 García-Ruiz, A., Crespo, J., López-de-Luzuriaga, J.M., Olmos, M.E., Monge, M., Rodríguez-
486 Alfaro, M.P., Martín-Álvarez, P.J., Bartolome, B., Moreno-Arribas, M.V., 2015. Novel
487 biocompatible silver nanoparticles for controlling the growth of lactic acid bacteria and
488 acetic acid bacteria in wines. *Food Control* 50, 613–619.
489 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCONT.2014.09.035>

490 Gupta, M., Karmakar, N., Sasmal, S., Chowdhury, S., Biswas, S., 2016. Free radical
491 scavenging activity of aqueous and alcoholic extracts of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* Linn.
492 measured by ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), ABTS bleaching assay

493 (α TEAC), DPPH assay and peroxy radical antioxidant assay. Int. J. Pharmacol. Toxicol.
494 4, 235. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijpt.v4i2.6578>

495 Gupta, V.K., Fatima, A., Faridi, U., Negi, A.S., Shanker, K., Kumar, J.K., Rahuja, N.,
496 Luqman, S., Sisodia, B.S., Saikia, D., Darokar, M.P., Khanuja, S.P.S., 2008.
497 Antimicrobial potential of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* roots. J. Ethnopharmacol. 116, 377–380.
498 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2007.11.037>

499 Hatano, T., Shintani, Y., Aga, Y., Shiota, S., Tsuchiya, T., Yoshida, T., 2000. Phenolic
500 constituents of licorice. VIII. Structures of glicophenone and glicoisoflavanone, and
501 effects of licorice phenolics on methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. Chem.
502 Pharm Bull. 48, 1286–1292.

503 Hedayati, A., Ghoreishi, S.M., 2016. Artificial neural network and adaptive neuro-fuzzy
504 interface system modeling of supercritical CO₂ extraction of glycyrrhizic acid from
505 *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. Chem. Prod. Process Model. 11, 217–230.
506 <https://doi.org/10.1515/cppm-2015-0048>

507 Hedayati, A., Ghoreishi, S.M., 2015. Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of glycyrrhizic
508 acid from licorice plant root using binary entrainer: Experimental optimization via
509 response surface methodology. J. Supercrit. Fluids 100, 209–217.
510 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2015.03.005>

511 Hejazi, I.I., Khanam, R., Mehdi, S.H., Bhat, A.R., Moshahid Alam Rizvi, M., Islam, A.,
512 Thakur, S.C., Athar, F., 2017. New insights into the antioxidant and apoptotic potential
513 of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. during hydrogen peroxide mediated oxidative stress: An in
514 vitro and in silico evaluation. Biomed. Pharmacother. 94, 265–279.
515 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2017.06.108>

516 Irani, M., Sarmadi, M., Bernard, F., Ebrahimi Pour, G.H., Shaker Bazarnov, H., 2010. Leaves
517 antimicrobial activity of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. Iran. J. Pharm. Res. IJPR 9, 425–8.

518 Karami, Z., Emam-Djomeh, Z., Mirzaee, H.A., Khomeiri, M., Mahoonak, A.S., Aydani, E.,
519 2015. Optimization of microwave assisted extraction (MAE) and soxhlet extraction of
520 phenolic compound from licorice root. J. Food Sci. Technol. 52, 3242–3253.
521 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-014-1384-9>

522 Karami, Z., Mirzaei, H., Emam-Djomeh, Z., Sadaghi Mohoonak, A.R., Khomeiri, M., 2013.
523 Effect of harvest time on antioxidant activity of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root extract and
524 evaluation of its antibacterial activity. Int. Food Res. J. 20, 2951–2957.

525 Kim, H.-S., Lee, S.-Y., Kim, B.-Y., Lee, E.-K., Ryu, J.-H., Lim, G.-B., 2004. Effects of
526 modifiers on the supercritical CO₂ extraction of *glycyrrhizin* from licorice and the
527 morphology of licorice tissue after extraction. biotechnol. bioprocess Eng. 9, 447–453.

528 Kondo, K., Shiba, M., Nakamura, R., Morota, T., Shoyama, Y., 2007. Constituent properties
529 of licorices derived from *Glycyrrhiza uralensis*, *G. glabra*, or *G. inflata* Identified by
530 Genetic Information. Biol. Pharm. Bull. 30, 1271–1277.
531 <https://doi.org/10.1248/bpb.30.1271>

532 Millao, S., Uquiche, E., 2016. Antioxidant activity of supercritical extracts from
533 *Nannochloropsis gaditana*: Correlation with its content of carotenoids and tocopherols.
534 J. Supercrit. Fluids 111, 143–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2016.02.002>

535 Mukhopadhyay, M., Panja, P., 2008. A novel process for extraction of natural sweetener from
536 licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) roots. Sep. Purif. Technol. 63, 539–545.
537 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2008.06.013>

538 NCCLS, 1999. Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. NCCLS,
539 Villanova.

540 Ody, P., 2000. The complete guide medicinal herbal. Dorling Kindersley.

541 Qiao, X., Song, W., Ji, S., Wang, Q., Guo, D.-A., Ye, M., 2015. Separation and
542 characterization of phenolic compounds and triterpenoid saponins in licorice

543 (*Glycyrrhiza uralensis*) using mobile phase-dependent reversed-phase × reversed-phase
544 comprehensive two-dimensional liquid chromatography coupled with mass
545 spectrometry. J. Chromatogr. A 1402, 36–45.
546 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2015.05.006>

547 Re, R., Pellegrini, N., Proteggente, A., Pannala, A., Yang, M., Rice-Evans, C., 1999.
548 Antioxidant activity applying an improved ABTS radical cation decolorization assay.
549 Free Radic. Biol. Med. 26, 1231–7.

550 Rufino, M. do S.M., Alves, R.E., de Brito, E.S., Pérez-Jiménez, J., Saura-Calixto, F.,
551 Mancini-Filho, J., 2010. Bioactive compounds and antioxidant capacities of 18 non-
552 traditional tropical fruits from Brazil. Food Chem. 121, 996–1002.
553 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.01.037>

554 Simmler, C., Pauli, G.F., Chen, S.-N., 2013. Phytochemistry and biological properties of
555 glabridin. Fitoterapia 90, 160–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2013.07.003>

556 Singleton, V.L., Orthofer, R., Lamuela-Raventós, R.M., 1999. Analysis of total phenols and
557 other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent. Methods
558 Enzymol. 299, 152–178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879\(99\)99017-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879(99)99017-1)

559 Skotti, E., Anastasaki, E., Kanellou, G., Polissiou, M., Tarantilis, P.A., 2014. Total phenolic
560 content, antioxidant activity and toxicity of aqueous extracts from selected Greek
561 medicinal and aromatic plants. Ind. Crops Prod. 53, 46–54.
562 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INDCROP.2013.12.013>

563 Thakur, D., Abhilasha, Jain, A., Ghoshal, G., 2016. Evaluation of phytochemical, antioxidant
564 and antimicrobial properties of glycyrrhizin extracted from roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*.
565 J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India). 75, 487–494.

566 Tohma, H.S., Gulçin, I., 2010. Antioxidant and Radical Scavenging Activity of Aerial Parts
567 and Roots of Turkish Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza Glabra* L.). Int. J. Food Prop. 13, 657–

568 671. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10942911003773916>

569 Villanueva-Bermejo, D., Zahran, F., García-Risco, M.R., Reglero, G., Fornari, T., 2017.

570 Supercritical fluid extraction of Bulgarian *Achillea millefolium*. J. Supercrit. Fluids 119,

571 283–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUPFLU.2016.10.005>

572 Visavadiya, N.P., Soni, B., Dalwadi, N., 2009. Evaluation of antioxidant and anti-atherogenic

573 properties of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root using in vitro models. International J. Food

574 Sci. Nutr. 60, 135–149. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09637480902877998>

575 Wei, S.-S., Yang, M., Chen, X., Wang, Q.-R., Cui, Y.-J., 2015. Simultaneous determination

576 and assignment of 13 major flavonoids and glycyrrhizic acid in licorices by HPLC-DAD

577 and Orbitrap mass spectrometry analyses. Chin. J. Nat. Med. 13, 232–240.

578 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1875-5364\(15\)30009-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1875-5364(15)30009-1)

579 Zhang, Q., Ye, M., 2009. Chemical analysis of the Chinese herbal medicine Gan-Cao

580 (licorice). J. Chromatogr. A 1216, 1954–1969.

581 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHROMA.2008.07.072>

582 **Table 1.** Experimental conditions and extraction yield (mass of extract/mass of raw material)
 583 obtained in the **supercritical extraction** of licorice roots. Extraction time: 3 h. (PS1) pressure
 584 in first separator, pressure in second separator was maintained at SCCO₂ recirculation
 585 pressure. **Run 1 – 8 at 313.15 K and 9 – 10 at 333.15 K.**

Run	Pressure (MPa)	CO₂ flow (g/min)	Ethanol (% mass)	P S1 (MPa)	Extraction yield (%)
1	15	70	0	5	0.66
2	15	70	10	5	2.19
3	15	50	5	5	1.64
4	15	50	10	5	2.01
5	15	50	15	5	2.48
6	15	50	20	5	3.07
7	30	70	0	15	1.76*
8	40	70	0	15	0.56*
9	30	70	0	15	0.74*
10	40	70	0	10	0.89*

586 *Extraction yield expressed as the sum of the mass collected from both separator vessels
 587 (S1 and S2).

588 **Table 2.** Extraction yield (mass of extract/mass of raw material) obtained in the S1 and S2
589 fractions of licorice roots extracts. Extraction time: 3 h. Pressure in first separator was 15
590 MPa and pressure in second separator was maintained at SCCO₂ recirculation pressure.

Run	Extraction yield in separators	
	(%mass)	
	S1	S2
7	0.24	1.52
8	0.06	0.50
9	0.09	0.65
10	0.27	0.62

591

592 **Table 3.** Mean values and standard deviations of **total phenolic compounds** (TPC) and
 593 antioxidant capacity (ABTS and DPPH assay) of licorice root supercritical extracts. S1: first
 594 separator fraction, S2: second separator fraction.

Run	TPC	ABTS		DPPH	
	(mg GAE/g extract)	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)	TEAC (µmol Trolox/g extract)	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)	TEAC (µmol Trolox/g extract)
1	76.2 ± 1.5	42.1 ± 3.2	102.2 ± 7.8	126.0 ± 0.5	112.5 ± 0.4
2	141.2 ± 1.1	28.4 ± 3.6	147.4 ± 13.7	32.4 ± 2.5	442.1 ± 34.2
3	153.0 ± 1.1	13.7 ± 0.1	312.5 ± 0.7	42.6 ± 0.9	331.4 ± 8.6
4	163.0 ± 1.3	13.0 ± 0.8	329.6 ± 21.1	37.8 ± 0.4	418.7 ± 4.4
5	174.9 ± 1.9	12.0 ± 0.1	358.6 ± 3.9	32.3 ± 0.4	440.8 ± 5.2
6	180.1 ± 0.9	7.7 ± 0.6	555.7 ± 45.7	18.6 ± 0.4	759.6 ± 16.2
7-S1	69.05 ± 0.9	105.3 ± 1.7	40.7 ± 0.7	248.1 ± 4.1	57.1 ± 0.9
7-S2	159.3 ± 1.2	33.3 ± 1.0	128.6 ± 4.0	42.8 ± 2.5	330.6 ± 9.0
8-S1	48.5 ± 3.6	44.7 ± 0.1	95.8 ± 0.3	185.8 ± 0.9	76.0 ± 0.4
8-S2	128.3 ± 3.4	11.84 ± 0.1	361.7 ± 3.0	21.9 ± 0.1	647.9 ± 3.1
9-S1	62.5 ± 2.5	38.8 ± 2.8	110.6 ± 7.9	149.5 ± 0.8	94.4 ± 0.5
9-S2	140.5 ± 7.7	10.3 ± 0.2	416.0 ± 8.9	54.4 ± 3.6	259.9 ± 17.3
10-S1	95.2 ± 8.7	15.7 ± 0.1	272.5 ± 0.2	74.0 ± 0.4	190.9 ± 0.6
10-S2	138.0 ± 8.9	7.7 ± 0.1	554.0 ± 6.6	59.2 ± 0.2	238.7 ± 0.7

595 **DPPH:** 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl

596 **ABTS:** 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt

597 **GAE:** Gallic acid equivalent

598 **IC₅₀:** Concentration of extract necessary to inhibit the initial concentration of radical by 50%

599 **TEAC:** Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity

600 **Table 4.** Antimicrobial activity of licorice root **supercritical** extracts.

Sample	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
	IC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	IC ₅₀ (mg/ml)
1	1.17	1.41
2	1.50	2.26
3	1.60	1.60
4	2.19	--
5	--	--
6	--	--
7-S1	0.76	1.49
7-S2	2.16	2.20
8-S1	1.86	2.00
8-S2	1.62	2.21
9-S1	1.30	1.49
9-S2	1.61	1.77
10-S1	1.02	1.36
10-S2	1.21	1.50
Chloramphenicol	0.08	0.09

601 **IC₅₀:** Concentration of extract required to obtain 50% inhibition of bacterial growth

602 **Table 5.** Concentration of bioactive compounds of **supercritical extracts** of licorice under
 603 different conditions.

Run	Liquiritin (mg/g)	Liquiritigenin (mg/g)	Glycyrrhizin (mg/g)	Isoliquiritigenin (mg/g)	Glabridin (mg/g)
1	0.40± 0.01	ND	0.80 ± 0.01	ND	49.50 ± 0.14
2	0.60± 0.01	0.80 ± 0.01	2.10 ± 1.27	1.40 ± 0.85	168.60 ± 1.70
3	0.80± 0.01	LLQ	1.20 ± 0.01	0.40 ± 0.01	198.10 ± 0.71
4	0.80± 0.01	1.60 ± 0.01	UDL	2.40 ± 0.01	192.10 ± 0.99
5	0.80± 0.01	1.80 ± 0.01	UDL	0.90 ± 0.14	151.50 ± 0.71
6	1.20± 0.01	2.60 ± 0.01	UDL	2.30 ± 1.27	147.40 ± 0.28

Concentration in samples S1 and S2

7-S1	UDL	ND	0.20 ± 0.01	ND	26.60 ± 1.41
7-S2	UDL	ND	0.70 ± 0.14	ND	140.80 ± 7.35
8-S1	UDL	ND	0.40 ± 0.01	ND	47.40 ± 7.07
8-S2	UDL	UDL	0.60 ± 0.01	UDL	143.50 ± 6.65
9-S1	0.20 ± 0.01	ND	0.70 ± 0.14	UDL	140.50 ± 0.99
9-S2	0.20 ± 0.01	UDL	0.60 ± 0.01	ND	74.40 ± 1.98
10-S1	UDL	UDL	0.40 ± 0.01	ND	118.30 ± 0.14
10-S2	0.80± 0.01	ND	0.80 ± 0.01	UDL	113.80 ± 0.01

Concentration in total extract (S1 + S2 samples)

7	UDL	ND	0.732± 0.14	ND	125.23 ± 6.54
8	UDL	UDL	0.579± 0.01	UDL	133.20 ± 6.70
9	0.20 ± 0.01	UDL	0.612± 0.03	UDL	82.44 ± 1.86
10	0.56 ± 0.01	UDL	0.679± 0.01	UDL	115.17 ± 0.04

604 ND: no detected

605 UDL: under detection limit

606

607 **Figure 1.** Extraction yield obtained in the **supercritical fluid extractions** of licorice root as a
 608 function of the amount of cosolvent (%mass). (●, ■) 15 MPa. Squares and circles
 609 correspond, respectively, to 50 and 70 g/min CO₂. The standard deviations obtained in
 610 duplicate experiments carried out in run 1 (**pure** CO₂) and run 3 (5% ethanol) are depicted in
 611 the figure.

612

613

614 **Figure 2. Supercritical fluids extractions** of licorice roots at 15 MPa, 313.15 K and 50 g/min
615 CO₂ flow: Effect of ethanol cosolvent addition in the extraction of phenolic compounds
616 expressed as mg of **gallic acid equivalent** (GAE)/ g of extract.

617

618 **Figure 3.** Total yield and **total phenolic compounds** (TPC) extracted (S1+S2 samples)
 619 obtained in runs 7 to 10. (■, □) 313.15 K; (●, ○) 333.15 K. Full symbols represent
 620 extraction yield and empty symbols represent TPC content.

621

622 **Figure 4.** Analysis of the relation between the IC₅₀ (Concentration of extract necessary to
 623 inhibit the initial concentration of radical by 50%) values of licorice supercritical extracts
 624 calculated with the ABTS and DPPH assay. (ABTS: 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-
 625 6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt; DPPH: 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl).

626

627 **Figure 5.** Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) vs. total phenolic compounds

628 (TPC) values of licorice root supercritical extracts: (□) ABTS and (■) DPPH assays.

629 (ABTS: 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt; DPPH:

630 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl).

(a)

(b)

632 **Figure 6.** Effect of pressure ((313.15 K, 70 g/min of CO₂ without cosolvent)) on the
 633 concentration and recovery of (a) glabridin and (b) glycyrrhizin: (■) concentration; (□)
 634 recovery.

635

636 **Figure 7.** Antibacterial activity of the most active samples (S1 fractions and extract of run 1):
 637 IC₅₀ (Concentration of extract required to obtain 50% inhibition of bacterial growth) values
 638 obtained for (□) *E. coli* and (▲) *S. aureus* as a function of the glabridin content.

639

640 **Figure 8.** Antioxidant activity: IC₅₀ (Concentration of extract necessary to inhibit the initial
641 concentration of radical by 50%) value obtained with the DPPH assay as a function of the
642 glabridin content.